

are you part of a small business who uses social media?

we are recruiting!

We're researchers at New York University and Cornell Tech studying how to improve digital safety for small businesses who have experienced harassment, fraud, or online abuse.

Sign up here

You'll receive a **\$40 gift card** for a one-hour confidential interview.

Your experiences will help us build tools and strategies to support people like you. **Thank you!**

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